

NANOTECHNOLOGY IN AGRICULTURAL CROP PRODUCTION: AN INTEGRATIVE LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The application of nanotechnology in achieving food security, better nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture is less explored in agricultural areas while the agriculture industry is currently threatened by various factors, including changing weather patterns, natural disasters, urbanization, and population growth. As a result, innovation is becoming increasingly necessary to survive, and the advancement of nanotechnology is an essential step toward developing a technology that has the potential to address problems in agricultural crop production. To evaluate the potential of various nanotechnology applications in improving crop productivity, the researcher examined various secondary data relevant to crop production and the application of nanotechnology using an integrative literature review. Upon reviewing the uses and results of nanotechnology in crop production based on data and findings from published studies, it is discovered that nano pesticides, nano fertilizers, nanosensors, and nanotechnology for controlling plant growth and seed germination have all been found to be highly beneficial in the quest to increase crop productivity. Extensive research on various agricultural topics has shown that nanotechnology has essential potential for enhancing crop output. Applications of nanotechnology unquestionably increase crop productivity. However, their stability still needs to be taken into account in praxis.

Keywords: *nanotechnology, nano fertilizers, nanosensors, nano pesticides, nanoparticles*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippine economy has historically depended on agriculture since crop production provides the raw materials essential to the food and feed industry sectors. Many crop production efforts have been made across the country to support family consumption and industry production, such as energy-efficient sustainable crop production (Gathala et al., 2020), straw management practices (Guan et al., 2020), climate-smart farming systems in high and low-input crop production (Richard et al., 2021), management of soilborne diseases (Panth, 2020), and other sustainable land management practices in extreme weather (McCarthy et al., 2021). In the agricultural sector, small-scale farmers are found to be reliant on conventional subsistence farming methods. Despite the efforts of government agencies, institutions, and non-governmental organizations to provide extension services, these farmers have yet to be successful in embracing new agricultural technologies.

The majority of small and marginalized farmers have remained technologically outdated and economically powerless due to (1) low investment in research and development, (2) inadequate education, and (3) ineffective transfer of agricultural technologies. With the increasing population, the Philippines may need help to produce or import food and products to meet the needs of the people. Thus, our country necessitates a robust and highly productive agricultural sector. The strength and productivity lie in the empowerment of the farmers and the promotion of agricultural technologies to enable our country to become highly competitive in the international market. The call for agricultural innovation became the center-shift for sustainable development; however, nanotechnology, which increases the quality and safety of food, including the technical capacity inputs of agricultural less soil by using nutrients management, is not widely employed in the Philippines due to a lack of broad implementation and support (Xiong et al., 2020).

Nanotechnology is a science, engineering, and technology conducted at the nanoscale, about 1 to 100 nanometers. To create structures, devices, and systems with at least one novel or superior characteristic or property, size, and shape at the nanoscale (atomic, molecular, and macromolecular) scale must be carefully manipulated during the design, characterization, production, and application phases. It primarily entails processing material consolidation, separation, and deformation by a single atom or molecule. To fully harness the unique quantum and surface phenomena that matter shows at the nanoscale, it enhances current industrial processes, materials, and applications by scaling them down to the nanoscale (Malik et al., 2023). Moreover, nanotechnology has the potential to revolutionize agriculture and food systems since the agricultural system has been facing many challenges with the growing population and the adverse effects of climate change.

Nonetheless, it is gaining much attention due to its expanding potential applications. In agriculture, ongoing research is on single molecule detection to determine

enzyme/substrate interactions, nanocapsules for delivery of pesticides, fertilizers, and other agrichemicals more efficiently, delivery of growth hormones, nanosensors for monitoring soil conditions and crop growth, nanochips for identity preservation and tracking, nanosensors for detection of animal and plant pathogens, nanocapsules to deliver vaccines, and nanoparticles to deliver DNA to plants (targeted genetic engineering).

Recently, nano biosensors, nano fertilizers, and nano pesticides are some of the applications of nanotechnology that are still being critiqued and have the potential to achieve a food-secure world. With these, the study aims to identify some of the nanotechnology applications to crop production and assess their potential for improving crop productivity by collecting and analyzing the findings of related studies.

Research Questions

In relevance to crop production and the application of nanotechnology, the researcher aims to assess the potential of various nanotechnology applications in crop productivity improvement.

Specifically, the study aims to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the different applications of nanotechnology in crop production?
2. What is the significance of nanotechnology applications to crop production?
3. What studies have been done that signify the potential of nanotechnology applications in crop production?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher used an integrative literature review (De Souza, 2010) to attempt to synthesize the collected research findings and data and to contrive the main idea of this study—the overall evaluation of nanotechnology and its applications in crop production. The emphasis of this design was the fitting and adequate description of the information gathered rather than judging or interpreting. Also, it aided in providing explanations to the questions laid out and validation of the various research findings. Altogether, a hypothesis was extracted from the analysis to conclude the main idea and support the objectives of this study.

RESULTS

Table 1. Articles surveyed in the databases on nanotechnology, nano fertilizers, nano pesticides, nanosensors

Area	Title of the article	Author	Journal (Volume, number, page, and year)	Considerations/Subject
Nanotechnology	Nanotechnology in Agriculture: Which Innovation Potential does it have?	Fraceto, L., Grillo, R., Medeiros, G., Scognamiglio, V., Rea, G. and Bartolucci, C.	Frontiers in Environmental Science, 4, 2016	It presents recent trends in nanomaterial-based systems and nanodevices engineered for controlled nutrient, pesticide, and fertilizer release in crops that could benefit sustainable intensification and soil and waste management.
	Nanotechnology in Sustainable Agriculture: Recent Developments, Challenges, and Perspectives	Prasad, R., Bhattacharyya, A. and Nguyen, Q.	Frontiers in Microbiology, 8, 1-2, 2017	It reviews the role of nanotechnology in enhancing agricultural advancements despite the existing challenges on sustainability, food security, and climate change.
	Nanotechnology: The new perspective in precision agriculture	Duhan, J., Kumar, R., Kumar, N., Kaur, P., Nehra, K. and Duhan, S.	Biotechnology Reports, 15, 11-23, 2017	It discusses nanotechnology's potential applications and benefits in precision agriculture, emphasizing nanoparticle-mediated delivery to plants.
	Trends in nanotechnology in the Philippines and Laos agricultural industry	Xiong, L., Concepcion, R., Santos, G., Gonzaga, J., Lim, J. and Dadios	HNICEM, 1-6, 2020	It explores nanotechnology trends as a modern agricultural innovation in the vegetable sustainable industry, healthy lifestyle, and take-off of the amount of fertilization, chemicals, and increased yield via nutrient solution.
	Nanoparticle-Based Sustainable Agriculture and Food Science: Recent Advances and Future Outlook	Mittal, D., Kaur, G., Singh, P., Yadav, K. and Ali, SA.	Frontiers in Nanotechnology, 2, 2020	It emphasizes the importance of nanotechnology in enhancing plant health and soil quality, improving disease resistance, crop yield, and nutrient absorption.
	Coping with the Challenges of Abiotic Stress in Plants: New Dimensions in the Field Application of Nanoparticles	Rajput, V.D., Minkina, T., Kumari, A., Harish, Singh, V.K., Verma, K.K., Mandzhieva, S., Sushkova, S., Srivastava, S., Keswani, C	Plants, 10, 2021	It is an analysis providing a comprehensive understanding of the mechanism of nanoparticle application in alleviating abiotic stresses in plants, heavy metals, salinity, and drought.
	Nanotechnological Interventions in Agriculture	Ahmad, Z., Tahseen, S., Wasi, A., Ganie, I.B., Shahzad, A., Emamverdian, A., Ramakrishnan, M. and Ding, Y.	Nanomaterials, 12, 2022	It provides information into leveraging plant nanotechnology to improve agricultural production vis-à-vis nanoparticles and the influence of nanotechnology in plant growth, development, pathogen detection, and crop protection, its role in the delivery of genetic material, plant growth regulators and agrochemicals and its role in genetic engineering.
	Role of Nanoparticles in Enhancing Crop Tolerance to Abiotic Stress: A Comprehensive Review	El-Saadony, M.T., Saad, A.M., Soliman, S.M., Salem, H.M., Desoky, E.M., Babalghith, A., El-Tahan, A., Ibrahim, O., Ebrahim, A., Abd El-Mageed, T.,	Frontiers of Plant Science, 13, 2022	It reviews the positive impacts of nanoparticles in sustainable agriculture as a practical tool to enhance crop yield and alleviate the harmful effects of abiotic stresses in crops.

		Elrys, A., Elbadawi, A., El-Tarably, K. and AbuQamar, S.		
	Multifaceted Role of Nanomaterials in Modulating In Vitro Seed Germination, Plant Morphogenesis, Metabolism and Genetic Engineering	Pathak, A., Haq, S., Meena, N., Dwivedi, P., Kothari, S.L., Kachhwaha, S	Plants, 12, 2023	Studies demonstrating the influence of nanoparticle treatments on seed germination, morphogenesis in vitro, and secondary metabolite levels assess the efficiency of nanoparticles in the genetic engineering of plants for safer gene delivery and for achieving transgenesis.
	The Role of Nanoparticles in the Response of Plants to Abiotic Stress at Physiological, Biochemical, and Molecular Levels	Al-Khayri, J.M., Rashmi, R., Surya Ulhas, R., Sudheer, W.N., Banadka, A., Nagella, P., Aldaej, M.I., Rezk, A.A.-S., Shehata, W.F., Almaghasla, M.I.	Plants, 12, 2023	It highlights both the capacity of nanoparticles to protect crop plants from diverse abiotic challenges such as salinity, high and low temperatures, heavy metals, and water scarcity and the mechanisms by which nanoparticles accumulate in plants.
Nanofertilizers	Effect of nanoscale zinc oxide particles on the germination, growth, and yield of peanut	Prasad, T.N.V.K.V., Sudhakar, P., Sreenivasulu, Y., Latha, P., Munaswamy, V., Raja Reddy, K., Sreeprasad, T.S., Sajanalal, P.R., and Pradeep, T.	Journal of Plant Nutrition, 35, 2012	It studies the effects of nanoscale zinc oxide particles on seed germination, seedling vigor, plant growth, flowering, chlorophyll content, pod yield, and root growth, which proved effective in increasing plant stem and root growth.
	Effects of Magnetite Nanoparticles on Soybean Chlorophyll	Mohammad, G.H., Mohammad, M.J., and Mohammad, D.R.	Environmental Science & Technology, 47, 2013	It reports on the impact of superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles (SPIONs) on soybean plants cultivated in a nanoparticle solution, which observed that it may affect the soybean chlorophyll content, potentially influencing biochemical and enzymatic efficiency during various stages of photosynthesis reactions.
	Effect of cerium oxide nanoparticles on the quality of rice (<i>Oryza et al.</i>) grains	Rico CM, Morales MI, Barrios AC, McCreary R, Hong J, Lee WY, Nunez J, Peralta-Videa JR, Gardea-Torresdey JL	Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 61, 47, 2013	This studies the quality of rice grains harvested from plants grown in soil treated with cerium oxide nanoparticles (nCeO ₂). The findings suggest that nano cerium oxide (nCeO ₂) may adversely affect the quality of rice.
	Synthetic apatite nanoparticles as a phosphorus fertilizer for soybean (<i>Glycine max</i>)	Liu, R., Lal, R.	SCIENTIFIC REPORTS, 4, 2014	Using apatite nanoparticles as a novel type of phosphorus fertilizer could improve agricultural yield by increasing growth rate and above-ground biomass production and lowering the risk of water eutrophication.
	Nanofertilizer use for sustainable agriculture: Advantages and limitations	Zulfiqar F, Navarro M, Ashraf M, Akram NA, Munné-Bosch S.	Plant Science, 289, 2019	This study signifies that nano fertilizers show potential in nutrition management by significantly boosting nutrient use efficiency through binding nutrients, either individually or in combinations, to nano-dimensional adsorbents, releasing them slowly compared to traditional fertilizers, which not only enhances nutrient utilization but also minimizes leaching into groundwater.
	Can Nanofertilizers Mitigate Multiple Environmental Stresses for Higher Crop Productivity?	Shalaby, T.A., Bayoumi, Y., Eid, Y., Elbasiouny, H., Elbehiry, F., Prokisch, J., El-Ramady, H. and Ling, W.	Sustainability, 14, 2020	It reviews the potential of nano fertilizers as an essential source of fertilizers, which can improve crop production, compared to traditional chemical fertilizers, and the role of nano fertilizers for plants under biotic and abiotic stresses.

	Efficacy of nanoparticles as nano fertilizer production: a review	Fatima F, Hashim A, Anees S.	Environmental Science and Pollution Research, 2, 2021	This review highlights the potential of nanofertilizers, addressing environmental and safety concerns. It also explores the introduction of various nanoparticle forms in agriculture, paving the way for nanotechnological advancements in farming.
	Urea-functionalized amorphous calcium phosphate nano fertilizers: optimizing the synthetic strategy towards environmental sustainability and manufacturing costs	Carmona, F.J., Dal Sasso, G., Ramírez-Rodríguez, G.B., Pii, Y., Delgado-López, J.M., Guagliardi, A., and Masciocchi, N.	Scientific Reports, 11, 2021	It reports on the promising features shown by Amorphous Calcium Phosphate (ACP) as a platform for multi-nutrient nano fertilizers, which then serve as a basis for developing an efficient method to incorporate urea-based N-macronutrients into ACP, which provides greater N-payloads, significantly higher efficiency (namely, use of 16.5 times less urea), and a doubled space-time yield.
	A novel P nano fertilizer does not impact soil microbial communities or activity.	Ciurli, A., Giagnoni, L., Pastorelli, R., Sega, D., Zamboni, A., Renella, G., Varanini, Z.	Applied Soil Ecology, 178, 2022.	It evaluates the effects of a new phosphorus nano fertilizer (P-NF) on phosphorus solubility, microbial toxicity, soil respiration rate, soil enzyme activity, and the composition of soil microbial communities. The newly tested phosphorus nano fertilizer (P-NF) could be utilized safely in agricultural practices.
	Nanofertilizers: A Smart and Sustainable Attribute to Modern Agriculture.	Nongbet, A., Mishra, A.K., Mohanta, Y.K., Mahanta, S., Ray, M.K., Khan, M., Baek, K.-H., Chakrabarty, I.	Plants, 11, 2022	This review presents the impact of nanoparticles that vary with the plant type and are influenced by their application, size, shape, and concentration. It shows that crop production can be significantly increased once the optimal dosage and plant requirements for nanofertilizers are established. It also suggests that future crop plants could significantly profit from environmentally friendly nano nutrition, particularly considering the recognized nanotoxicological impacts of nanomaterials and nanoparticles.
Nanopesticides	Antifungal Effects of Silver Nanoparticles (AgNPs) against Various Plant Pathogenic Fungi	Kim, SW., Jung, J.H., Lamsal, K., Kim, YS., Min, J.S., and Lee, Y.S.	Mycobiology 40, 53-58, (2012)	It studies the efficacy of silver compounds for use in controlling plant pathogens in which the inhibition effect of three different AgNPs (WA-CV-WA13B, WA-AT-WB13R, and WA-PR-WB13R) against various plant pathogenic fungi in vitro is examined.
	Development of a new method to prepare nano-/microparticles loaded with extracts of <i>Azadirachta indica</i> , their characterization, and use in controlling <i>Plutella xylostella</i>	Forim, M.R., Costa, E.S., da Silva, M.F., Fernandes, J.B., Mondego, J.M., Boiça Junior, A.L.	Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 61, 38, 2013	It introduces a novel approach for creating nanoparticles containing neem <i>Azadirachta indica</i> extracts, demonstrating complete larval mortality in <i>Plutella xylostella</i> .
	Nanopesticides: Guiding Principles for Regulatory Evaluation of Environmental Risks	Kookana, R.S., Boxall, A., Reeves, P., Ashauer, R., Beulke, S., Chaudhry, Q., Cornelis, G., Fernandes, T., Gan, J., Kah, M., Lynch, I., Ranville, J., Sinclair, C., Spurgeon, D., Tiede, T., and Van den Brink, P.	Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 62, 2014	As nano pesticides offer a promising advancement due to their enhanced efficacy and potential for safeguarding the environment and human health, this review examines current approaches for environmental risk assessment of pesticides in which their environmental behavior and effects may vary from traditional pesticides. It also explores potential adjustments to assessment tests and procedures, covering aspects like analysis, environmental fate, exposure assessment, ecotoxicity, and risk evaluation in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems.
	Nanopesticides and Nanofertilizers: Emerging Contaminants or Opportunities for Risk Mitigation?	Kah, M.	Frontiers in Chemistry, 3, 64, 2015	It evaluates the future of nano agrochemicals as a potential source of emerging solutions to mitigate pesticide contamination.

	Biosynthesized silver nanoparticles as a nano weapon against phytopathogens: exploring their scope and potential in agriculture	Mishra, S., Singh, H.B.	Applied Microbiology Biotechnology, 99, 3, 2015	It highlights the potential utilization of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) in agriculture, particularly for managing plant diseases, the interactions of AgNPs with the agricultural environment, including soil, soil organisms, and plants, with a focus on mitigating factors contributing to toxicity, and the significance of employing microbes and plants for AgNPs synthesis instead of relying on chemical methods.
	Nanoencapsulation, Nano-guard for Pesticides: A New Window for Safe Application	Nuruzzaman, M., Rahman, M.M., Liu, Y., Naidu, R.	Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 64, 7, 2016	It reviews how nanoencapsulation techniques with slow-releasing properties and enhanced solubility, permeability, and stability can improve the delivery of pesticides.
	Zein Nanoparticles as Eco-Friendly Carrier Systems for Botanical Repellents Aiming Sustainable Agriculture	Oliveira, J.L., Campos, E.V.R., Pereira, A.E.S., Pasquoto, T., Lima, R., Grillo, R., Andrade, D.J., Santos, F.A.D., Fraceto, L.F.	Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry, 66, 6, 2018	It evaluates the phytotoxicity, cytotoxicity, and insect activity of the nanoparticles toward target and nontarget organisms by using zein nanoparticles loaded with the main constituents of the essential oil of citronella (geraniol and R-citronellal).
	Advances in Biopolymeric Nanopesticides: A New Eco-Friendly/Eco-Protective Perspective in Precision Agriculture	Kumar, R., Kumar, N., Rajput, V.D., Mandzhieva, S., Minkina, T., Saharan, B.S., Kumar, D., Sadh, P.K., Duhan, J.S.	Nanomaterials, 12, 2022	It provides an in-depth examination of the toxicity and release characteristics of biopolymeric nanopesticides designed for precise delivery in crop protection strategies.
	Aggregation, Sedimentation, and Dissolution of Cu(OH) ₂ -Nanorods-Based Nanopesticide in Soil Solutions	Xu, Z.; Tang, Q.; Hong, A.; Li, L	Nanomaterials, 12, 2022	It focuses on the role of Cu(OH) ₂ nano pesticide in the soil environment, which is necessary for the risk assessment of nanomaterials-based agrochemicals.
	Advanced nano pesticides: Advantage and action mechanisms	Li, X., Chen, Y., Lynch, I., Guo, Z., Xie, C., Zhang, P.	Plant Physiology Biochemistry 203, 2023	It provides an overview of the advantages and effects of nanoparticles compared to conventional pesticides, examining the formation and functions of nanoparticles in terms of structure, active ingredients, and additives, and describes the mechanism of action of nanoparticles.
Nanosensors	Implications of Nanobiosensors in Agriculture	Rai, V., Acharya, S., Dey, N.	Journal of Biomaterials and Nanobiotechnology, 3, 2012	It investigates how nano biosensors can contribute to sustainable agriculture by improving crop productivity as a tool for detecting a diverse range of fertilizers, herbicides, pesticides, insecticides, pathogens, moisture levels, and soil pH.
	Nanosensor Technology Applied to Living Plant Systems	Kwak, S.Y., Wong, M.H., Lew, T.T.S., Bisker, G., Lee, M., Kaplan, A., Dong, J., Liu, A.T., Koman, V., Sinclair, R., Hamann, C., Strano, M.	Annual Review of Analytical Chemistry, 10, 2017	It explores how nanosensors can be applied to various aspects of plant biology, including nutrient management, disease assessment, food production, detection of DNA proteins, and the regulation of plant hormones.
	Nanobiotechnology approaches for engineering smart plant sensors.	Giraldo, J.P., Wu, H., Newkirk, G.M., Kruss, S.	Nature Nanotechnology, 14, 6, 2019	It offers a comprehensive perspective on the potential of nanotechnology to facilitate the development of intelligent plant sensors that communicate with and control electronic devices for monitoring and optimizing individual plant productivity and resource use.
	Monitoring Plant Health with Near-Infrared Fluorescent H ₂ O ₂ Nanosensors	Wu, H., Nißler, R., Morris, V., Herrmann, N., Hu, P., Jeon, S.J., Kruss, S., Giraldo, J.P.	Nano Letters, 20, 4, 2020	It investigates the utilization of near-infrared (nIR) fluorescent single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs) interfaced with Arabidopsis thaliana plant leaves to detect initial signs of plant stress to enhance human understanding of plant stress communication,

				to provide innovative tools for precision agriculture, and refine the application of agrochemicals in the environment.
	Contributions of Nano Biosensors in Managing Environmental Plant Stress Under Climatic Changing Era	Kordrostami, M., Mafakheri, M., Al-Khayri, J.M.	Nanobiotechnology, 117–137, 2021	It provides an overview of recent developments in nano biosensors aimed at advancing global food security as the effects of climate change become increasingly evident.
	A Review on Biosensors and Nanosensors Application in Agroecosystems	Sharma, P., Pandey, V., Sharma, M.M.M., Patra, A., Singh, B., Mehta, S., Husen, A.	Nanoscale Research Letters, 16, 1, 2021	It reviews various bio and nanosensors used to monitor agricultural ecosystems and underscores the factors influencing the transition of nanosensors from proof-of-concept to commercialization.
	Carbon-Based Nanomaterials for Sustainable Agriculture: Their Application as Light Converters, Nanosensors, and Delivery Tools	Zhu, L., Chen, L., Gu, J., Ma, H., Wu, H.	Plants, 11, 511, 2022	It discusses how carbon-based nanomaterials are crucial in boosting food production and supporting agricultural sustainability, focusing on their roles as biosensors, carriers, and light converters.
	Nanosensor Applications in Plant Science	Shaw, D.S., Honeychurch, K.C.	Biosensors (Basel), 24,12, 9, 2022	It studies the various applications of nanosensors in plants, which have become crucial instruments for observing biological activities like plant signaling pathways and metabolism in ways that are non-destructive, minimally invasive, and offer real-time analysis capabilities.
	Potential of nano biosensor in sustainable agriculture: the state-of-art	Mondal, R., Dam, P., Chakraborty, J., Paret, M.L., Kati, A., Altuntas, S., Sarkar, R., Ghorai, S., Gangopadhyay, D., Mandal, A.K., Husen, A.	Heliyon, 8, 8, 12, 2022	It explores the different types of nano biosensors tailored to specific applications in the agricultural sector, highlighting their potential to revolutionize conventional farming practices by facilitating the early detection and management of various abnormalities in crops and soil.
	Nanobiosensors and nanoformulations in agriculture: new advances and challenges for sustainable agriculture	Miguel-Rojas C, Pérez-de-Luque A.	Emerging topics in life sciences, 7, 229–238, 2023	It provides a summary of the latest creative applications of nano fertilizers and nano biosensors in agriculture, which can enhance crop protection and productivity while mitigating the adverse environmental effects associated with agricultural practices.

Table 2. *Synthesis of uses, results, interpretation of nanotechnology, nano fertilizers, nano pesticides, nanosensors*

Synthesis	Uses	Result	Interpretation
Nutrition management through nano fertilizers	It increases nutrient use efficiency by enhancing plant nutrient uptake. It also resists degradation by hydrolysis, photolysis, evaporation, microbial organism decomposition, and weathering.	"Nanoparticles' high specific surface area, high stability, and excellent biocompatibility provide N.P. fertilizer composites with increased release efficiency. One study shows that urea-hydroxyapatite (H.A.) N.P.s have exhibited great potential for prolonging the release time and reducing the consumption of nitrogen fertilizers. Urea obtains the advantages of N.P.s by interacting with amine and carbonyl	It can improve plant nutrition by promoting fertilizer absorption and increasing crop yields. It can also facilitate nutrient uptake through encapsulating fertilizers with nanoparticles as these are hardly damaged by environmental factors such as rain and wind and are easily transferred into plant cells. The size distribution of N.P.s is an effective parameter related to fertilization

		groups of HA NPs. Field trial data have shown that compared with pure urea, nano hybrids of urea and Hydroxyapatite increase agronomic nitrogen use efficiency by approximately 30%. Another instance is the loading of N, P, and K into chitosan N.P.s, which increases the acquisition of N, P, and K by 17.04%, 16.31%, and 67.50%, respectively, compared to untreated control in cultured coffee plants.”	efficiency. Interestingly, nanotype fertilizers all have decreased particle sizes and increased numbers of particles per unit, leading to high specific surface areas. Increased interaction with leaves and roots enables plants to better absorb fertilizers. In addition, the unique properties of N.P.s lead to enduring effects.
Advancing pest control through nanopesticides	Nanopesticides are used to treat pest-related diseases and control weeds. It is also used to decrease herbicide residues in the environment and increase weed control efficiency.	“It decreases chemical pesticide doses, increases crop production, and promotes sustainable development. Nanotype insecticides are more efficient at killing pests and less likely to cause side effects on humans. One instance is spinosad- and permethrin-loaded chitosan N.P.s applied to fruit fly <i>Drosophila melanogaster</i> displayed reinforced bioavailability even at lower doses than free spinosad and free permethrin, and the nanocomposites caused decreased damages to humans and the ecological environment. Among various kinds of N.P.s, solid lipids are the most suitable nanocarriers for nanoherbicides due to their excellent chemical stability and simple metabolism. Another instance is the foliar application of metsulfuron methyl-loaded polysaccharide N.P.s to weeds growing in wheat, which significantly decreases the weed biomass compared with the average herbicide. Moreover, the cytotoxicity of nano herbicides and traditional herbicides was also detected by incubation with cells, and the results showed that herbicide-loaded N.P.s were less toxic than regular herbicides.”	It can aid in pest control populations by amplifying the advantages of sex pheromones as the case of methyl eugenol-loaded nanogels applied to guava orchards increased the number of trap catches compared with the control group containing only methyl eugenol. Regarding crop production, nano pesticides play a significant role in increasing the activity of insecticides and decreasing toxicity towards humans by having stability and a slow release capacity upon encapsulation by N.P.s counterparts. In addition, they have concentrated particle size distributions and large specific surface areas, which improve antifungal activity and prolong fungicide release times. Nanopesticides have been promising management tools to prevent viral invasion in different ways, such as by interacting with nucleic acids, triggering plant immune responses, and delivering RNA interference systems.
Stabilizing plant growth and development through nanosensors	They are involved in nutrient management, growth monitoring, pest and disease assessment, soil conditions detection, food production, and plant hormone detection. Nanosensors constitute a new platform for monitoring plant growth and development, which achieves non-destructive and accurate monitoring and can be applied to individual plants in real time. They are used in living plants as plant signals, growth, and stress sensors.	“These are significant in plant disease diagnosis, particularly when monitoring plant health and taking immediate defensive actions. Nanosensors assist researchers in recognizing plant pathogens promptly. Targets of plant disease are identified by nanosensors, including DNA, protein, and volatile organic compounds (VOCs). One example is when compared with the standard polymerase chain reaction method, the SERS-recombinase polymerase amplification (RPA) method is more sensitive and had a lower limit of detection in recognizing three essential plant pathogens, Gray mold <i>Botrytis cinerea</i> , Bacterial canker <i>Pseudomonas syringae</i> and Fusarium wilt of banana <i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> . Another example is the use of flexible electronic sensing devices developed to continuously monitor water transportation, sap flow, and nutrient distribution. Applying this nanosensor to watermelon revealed a day/night shift in water distribution between fruits	Nanosensors help monitor plant health at the molecular level, which dramatically increases the efficiency of plant management through multiple plant signaling molecules such as phytohormones and the emergence of wearable plant nanosensors for monitoring plant growth parameters; however, the stability of these nanosensors still needs to be considered more when leveraged in agricultural systems.

		and leaves through monitoring water transportation and distribution are significant biological signs of progress in plant growth and development.”	
Nanotechnology for Seed Germination and Plant Growth Regulation	It is used in various aspects of agricultural production, such as seed germination and plant growth, to increase crop yields and quality.	<p>“Seed germination is related to antioxidant enzyme activities and the contents or utilization rates of water and oxygen, such as that of the study in which Au NPs significantly increased the germination rate of pearl millet compared to that of untreated plants. The seed germination rate of wheat treated with ZnO N.P.s was increased compared with that of the control group. N.P.s, as shown in other studies such as CNTs, silicon dioxide (SiO₂) N.P.s, ZnO N.P.s, titanium dioxide (TiO₂) N.P.s, and even gold (Au) N.P.s, have positive effects on seed germination in crop plants, including tomato, wheat, rice, pearl millet, soybean, barley, and maize. Seed germination is related to antioxidant enzyme activities and the contents or utilization rates of water and oxygen. Both NPs mentioned above can increase antioxidant enzyme activity. TiO₂ NPs are beneficial to promoting seed germination, and exogenous treatment with TiO₂ NPs enhances the seed's absorption of water and oxygen, leading to decreased germination time. For instance, tomato seeds soaked with TiO₂ NPs exhibited a germination percentage increase of approximately 8% compared with the untreated control. Another study has revealed that TiO₂ NPs stimulate seed germination and dramatically decrease mean germination time in wheatgrass. Moreover, nonmetallic N.P.s such as multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) can promote seed germination in different crops by increasing the seed water assimilation capability. Air-spraying MWCNTs on soybean, barley, and corn seeds successfully increased the seed germination rate by at least 25% compared with the untreated control.”</p>	Nanoparticles can promote the growth, photosynthesis, and yield of many crop species, such as maize and soybean. It can also contribute to the acceleration of plant growth by mediating crop antioxidant enzyme activity. It can also influence plant cell morphology and improve the cell's protein and organic compounds content. However, instances may occur, such as N.P.s inducing intracellular oxidative stress and genetic damage, leading to reduced crop yields and physiological disorders when applying high concentrations of N.P.s. Hence, the safest doses of various N.P.s for different crop species must be determined.

DISCUSSION

The four (4) syntheses below show an in-depth discussion of Table 2 on *uses, results, and interpretations of nanotechnology nano fertilizers, nano pesticides, and nanosensors,*

Synthesis 1: *Nutrition management through nano fertilizers*

Nanofertilizers are nanomaterials that provide nutrients to plants to enhance their growth and health, allowing the nutrients to be released into the soil in a gradual and controlled way and preventing water resource pollution compared to traditional fertilizers. These have unique features like ultrahigh absorption, increase in production, photosynthesis, and significant expansion in the leaves' surface area. Nanomaterials can encapsulate nutrients in nano fertilizers, be coated with a thin protective film, or be delivered as emulsions or nanoparticles (Berger, M., 2021).

The advantages of nano fertilizers include increased efficiency of their constituents, lower soil toxicity, and a reduced frequency of fertilizer application. Maize treated with nanoparticles of titanium oxide (TiO₂) showed improvements in growth, whereas maize treated with TiO₂ in bulk had no significant changes⁸). Another example is soybeans treated with silicon oxide (SiO₂) and TiO₂ nanoparticles to improve nitrate reductase activity and increase plant absorption capacity. Three types of nutrients are delivered by nano fertilizers: macronutrients, micronutrients, and nanoparticles. Macronutrients are needed in large quantities and are vital for plant growth. The macronutrient fertilizer requirement will increase as the demand for food production increases. The fertilizer requirement will be up to 263 MT by 2050⁹). Nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, sulfur, and calcium are essential macronutrients for plant growth¹⁰). The high-volume-to-surface ratio of macronutrient nano fertilizers reduces the amount needed and increases the efficiency compared to traditional fertilizers (Berger, M., 2021).

The use of nano fertilizer leads to increased efficiency of the elements, reduces the toxicity of the soil to at least reaches the adverse effects caused by the excessive consumption of fertilizers, and reduces the frequency of application of fertilizers. Nanobased slow-release or C.R. fertilizers can increase the efficiency of nutrient uptake. Engineered nanoparticles help mitigate the chronic problem of moisture retention in arid soils and enhance crop production by increasing the availability of nutrients in the rhizosphere. Improving production has been observed through the foliar application of nanoparticles as fertilizer. The positive morphological effects included enhanced germination percentage and rate; length of root and shoot and their ratio; and vegetative biomass of seedlings in many crop plants, including corn, wheat, ryegrass, alfalfa, soybean, rape, tomato, radish, lettuce, spinach, onion, pumpkin and cucumber. Many physiological parameters, such as enhanced photosynthetic activity and nitrogen metabolism, are enhanced by metal-based nanomaterials in a few crops, including soybean, spinach, and peanut (Sekhon, B., 2014).

Synthesis 2: *Advancing pest control through nano pesticides*

In recent years, nanomaterials have been considered an alternative solution to control plant pathogens. Agricultural practices usually include systematically applying a wide array of active compounds at variable dosages and frequencies, representing a wide range of selective regimes. Insect pests are a predominant issue in agriculture, making nanopesticides a key player in controlling insect pests and host pathogens. Recently, a nanoencapsulated pesticide formulation was developed. This type of pesticide has slow-

releasing properties with enhanced solubility, specificity, permeability, and stability. The properties of the nanopesticide are kept intact by protecting the active ingredients in the capsule from premature degradation or by enhancing their pest control efficacy for a more extended period (Prasad, R., 2017). The recent development of a nanoencapsulated pesticide formulation has slow-releasing properties with enhanced solubility, specificity, permeability, and stability. These assets are mainly achieved by protecting the encapsulated active ingredients from premature degradation or increasing their pest control efficacy for longer. The formulation of nanoencapsulated pesticides led to a reduction in the dosage of pesticides and human beings' exposure to them, which is environmentally friendly for crop protection. Microencapsulation-like nanoencapsulation is used to develop the quality of products of desired chemicals delivered to the target biological process (Prasad, R., 2017). Nanopesticides such as Ag, Cu, SiO₂, ZnO, and nanoformulations show better broad-spectrum pest protection efficiency in comparison with conventional pesticides. Development of these non-toxic and promising pesticide delivery systems for increasing global food production while reducing the negative environmental impacts on ecosystems.

Biotic factors also largely influence crop productivity, including pests and diseases. Farmers have been heavily reliant on pesticides to minimize crop losses, which adversely affect human health and environmental sustainability. However, recent studies have shown that nanopesticides could reduce the risks of pests and diseases, thereby minimizing the severity of yield losses and ecological hazards (Shang et al., 2019). Indeed, in recent years, nanomaterials have been considered an alternative solution to control plant pathogens. Researchers have made significant efforts toward the synthesis of nanoparticles through various means, including physical, chemical, and biological methods. Green methods for synthesizing nanoparticles with plant extracts are advantageous as they are simple, convenient, environmentally friendly, and require less reaction time. Nanomaterials prepared by eco-friendly and green methods may increase agriculture's potential for improving fertilization, plant growth, and pesticides. In addition, this technology minimizes the amount of harmful chemicals that pollute the environment. With the growing need to reduce the use of environmentally risky substances, such as insecticides, the biosynthesis of nanoparticles, an emerging highlight of the intersection of nanotechnology and biotechnology, has received increasing attention. The reduction rate of metal ions using plants is much faster than microorganisms and stable formation of nanoparticles. Nanopesticides such as antimicrobial agents and nanofungicides can be utilized to control plant pests and even plant viruses. Nanopesticides have a practical impact on plant growth and molecular farming with the help of nano vectors, hoping to replace viral vectors (Ghidan, A., 2020).

Synthesis 3. *Stabilizing plant growth and development through nanosensors*

Nanosensors are devices that respond to small environmental changes and convert them into proper forms of information. Nanobiosensors is a modified version of a biosensor which may be defined as a compact analytical device/ unit incorporating a biological or biologically derived sensitized element linked to a physico-chemical transducer and is a combined knowledge of biology, chemistry, and nanotechnology to

improve crop productivity. These detect chemical species such as microbes, contaminants, pollutants, and food freshness and monitor environmental conditions. Taken together, proper and controlled use of nano biosensors can support sustainable agriculture and enhance crop productivity.

There are various types of nanobiosensors: 1) Mechanical, 2) Optical, 3) Nanowire, 4) Ion Channel Switch, 5) Electronic, 6) Viral, 7) PEEBLE, and 8) Nanoshell. The development of these is also one of the strengths of nanotechnology despite its early development stage and a few commercialized technologies. In terms of advantages, nano biosensors are ultra-sensitive. They can detect single virus particles or even ultra-low concentrations of a substance that could be potentially harmful, work at atomic scale with highest efficiency, and have increased surface to volume ratio. However, these are also disadvantageous since they are susceptible, error-prone and are still in infancy (Rai et al., 2012).

The application of nano biosensors in crop protection helps in the identification of diseases and residues of agrochemicals. In precision farming, nano biosensors connected with a global positioning system (GPS) navigation system help in real-time monitoring of soil environments, crop growth, as well as precise application of fertilizers and pesticides. These are also used to closely assess environmental conditions, plant status, and growth.

Synthesis 4. *Nanotechnology for Seed Germination and Plant Growth Regulation*

Nanotechnology also involves the development of approaches to a range of inexpensive nanotech applications for enhanced seed germination, plant growth, development and acclimation to environments. The germination of seeds is a sensitive phase in the life cycle of a plant, which facilitates seedling development, survival, and population dynamics. However, seed germination is primarily affected by different parameters, including environmental factors, genetic traits, moisture availability, and soil fertility. Therefore, studies have shown that the application of nanomaterials has positive effects on germination and plant growth and development. For example, nano SiO₂, TiO₂, and Zeolite applications positively stimulate seed germination in crop plants. In addition to germination, nanomaterials, such as ZnO, TiO₂, MWCNTs, FeO, ZnFeCu-oxide, and hydroxy fullerenes, are reported to increase crop growth and development with quality enhancement in many crop species, including peanut, soybean, mungbean, wheat, onion, spinach, tomato, potato and mustard. Similarly, applying nanomaterials positively affects germination and plant growth and development. For example, applying multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) positively influences seed germination of different crop species, including tomato, corn, soybean, barley, wheat, maize, peanut, and garlic.

Moreover, the studies of nutrients on slow/controlled release or control loss of nano fertilizers carried out in water and soil have confirmed that the long-term availability of all the doped nutrients to the plant over the entire crop period of cultivation is crucial for promoting germination, growth, flowering, and fruiting. These results from nanomaterials have the potential to penetrate the seed coat and enhance the ability to absorb and utilize

water, which stimulates enzymatic systems and ultimately improves germination and seedling growth. These findings revealed perspectives of nanomaterials to improve crop yields and product quality. However, the mechanism of nanomaterial-induced water uptake inside the seed is still largely unknown; thus, it is still an area for research (Shang et al., 2019).

Conclusions

Based on the obtained data, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Nanofertilizers, nanopesticides, nanosensors, and nanotechnology for seed germination and plant growth regulation significantly contribute to crop productivity. These nanotechnology applications facilitate nutrient uptake, increase the activity of insecticides while decreasing toxicity towards humans, help monitor plant health at the molecular level, and promote the growth, photosynthesis, and yield of many crop species.
 2. Nanotechnology applications involve nanoparticles encapsulating fertilizer components such as loading N, P, and K into chitosan N.P.s that increase the acquisition of N, P, and K by 17.04%, 16.31%, and 67.50%, respectively. Spinosad- and permethrin-loaded chitosan nanoparticles were utilized as nano pesticides to fruit fly *Drosophila melanogaster*, which displayed reinforced bioavailability even at lower doses. One example is the utilization of nanosensors for plant disease diagnosis that is significant for monitoring plant health and taking immediate defensive actions such as having a lower limit of detection in recognizing three essential plant pathogens, *Botrytis cinerea*, *Pseudomonas syringae*, and *Fusarium oxysporum*. Another example is using nanomaterials for seed germination as it is related to antioxidant enzyme activities and the contents or utilization rates of water and oxygen, and another on Au nanoparticles significantly increasing the germination rate of pearl millet.
 3. Applications of nanotechnology have been researched, and the results show that it has the potential to provide creative solutions to enhance sustainable agriculture and meet food demands. These solutions include monitoring plant growth status, addressing various agricultural issues, such as the overuse of pesticides and fertilizers, and significantly promoting plant growth and seed germination. Nanotechnology increases crop productivity, improves crop tolerance, and reduces environmental pollution, though its stability still needs to be considered.
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Recommendations

The researchers at this moment propose the following recommendations:

1. Explore applications of nanotechnology in other agricultural areas, such as horticulture, animal production, food storage, and processing;

2. Assess the positive and negative effects of nanotechnology applications to further identify its implications in multiple applications across various areas of modern science, including physics, pharmacology, chemistry, food and agriculture, and agricultural engineering. This can either support or refute the claim that nanotechnology is an innovative solution to global challenges such as but not limited to food demands and environmental pollution.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study has mainly involved an intensive review of related published studies and literature due to the current circumstances and inaccessible tools and equipment for the actual experiment. Obtaining relevant data from secondary sources was supported by Xavier University's online database and other scholarly sources. The study has no actual experiments and the potential influence of the applications of nanotechnology to other areas of agriculture, such as animal production.

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